

Comments on Input from Public Consultation on the TRUST Code Supplement

17 September 2025

We are very grateful for the input provided during the public consultation on the TRUST Code Supplement. **We were also very gratified that we received so many positive comments**, especially about the need to have something like the TRUST Code Supplement.

Overarching comments

We noticed four overall things:

1) **Overlap with the TRUST Code**

Many commentators asked us to provide additional details on topics that are already covered by the TRUST Code. With our short, values-based, jargon-free codes, we want to avoid duplication wherever possible. In particular, the TRUST Code Supplement relies heavily on the TRUST Code (hence, the name ‘supplement’). For this reason, those comments could not be accommodated. Instead, we added an additional sentence to the preface: **“Accordingly, the TRUST Code forms the foundation for research in fragile settings, while this Supplement furthers its applicability in these contexts.”**

Or another example. We completely agree that long-term relationships are key to trust and equitable partnerships, as one commentator pointed out. That’s why this has been promoted through the TRUST Code (2018). The TRUST Code says in its Preamble: “Those applying the Code oppose double standards in research and support long-term equitable research relationships...”. Likewise, the TRUST Code counters extractive research, which therefore does not need to be repeated in the Supplement.

2) **Supplementary Materials requested**

Another set of commentators asked for supplementary materials, for instance, structured risk assessment frameworks or voluntary self-assessments. Or they asked for specific examples, for instance, how to do community engagement (e.g. through engaging local council leaders). Based upon feedback from adopters of the TRUST Code (2018) over the years, we know that its global success stems in part from not prescribing specific solutions. Whilst the code’s articles clearly identify the problems (for example, the potential exploitation of interpreters or other support staff), they deliberately stop short of prescribing solutions (such as offering guidance on how interpreters should be rewarded).

Local solutions need to be found locally rather than specific solutions being prescribed by a code. This is the inclusive foundation of the TRUST Code and its Supplement.

We are always very grateful for supplementary materials produced by TRUST Code adopters or TRUST Code ‘friends’. For instance, [Coningham et al](#) applied the TRUST Code to assess, retrospectively, whether a post-earthquake collaboration between Nepal and the UK was equitable. A lot of practical advice can be gained from such efforts to apply the TRUST Code to existing collaborations, but it would be inappropriate to try and capture such specifics *inside* the code itself.

3) Problems in all settings

Several requests for new articles or enhancements to existing articles were made that are relevant across all settings, not just fragile settings, such as the ethical challenges of cross-border data transfers. As these issues are not specific to fragile settings, they are not explicitly addressed in the TRUST Code Supplement.

4) Additional recommendations

Some fantastic proposals were made, such as developing localized versions of the code that are co-created with community leaders, civil society, and local researchers. As our funding ended on 31 August 2025, high-resource suggestions like these cannot be taken up by us. Nevertheless, we would encourage further developments by others through local initiatives.

Other comments

5) Visual readability

We are very grateful for the comment that the front page has not been designed for readability for the visually impaired. A new front page has been designed.

6) Scientific rigour

We agree that scientific rigour can be compromised in fragile settings and potentially even compromised unnecessarily as the setting might be used as an excuse for unreliable data collection. We hope that we tackled the latter through invoking the value of fairness:

Article 15

Research participants’ time is precious when sustaining life and health takes priority. It is therefore important that the resulting research is likely to be of good enough quality to lead to meaningful results. **If the integrity of the research is likely to be compromised, people must not be burdened with participation.**

We hope it is clear that the TRUST Code Supplement strongly condemns research that lacks rigor.

7) Use of academic language

Whilst we understand that a code, which uses language such as “an intersectional approach” would emphasize that the code promotes the rights of disempowered people in difficult power dynamics, the TRUST Family Ethics Codes (four now) are written in such a way that no specialist knowledge is required to understand them.

8) Too absolute

Articles are phrased too absolutely, according to one commentator’s feedback. This person wrote a very eloquent 350-word comment on the absoluteness of Article 1 (The physical integrity, mental health and safety of people in fragile settings must not be further worsened through their involvement in research.) taking a stance for the right of people to take risks with their life and health to counter misinformation. We fully understand this comment. However, we believe that this task is better left to journalists. Ethics codes that are written in favour of advocacy miss the main point, namely, to protect those who take part in the research process. **However, we did change the term ‘must’ in Article 1, to ‘should’, as an acknowledgement of the complexities.**

9) Definition of Fragile Setting

To be practical, we specified very specific fragile settings in the preface. This was necessary, because the TRUST Code Supplement is research-based. We examined research evidence in the settings that are specified: “disaster or post-disaster areas, conflict or post-conflict zones, or high-crime informal settlements.” We valued the comment that framing fragile through a deficit model overlooks local resilience. However, to preserve the link between the research evidence and the articles, it is necessary to retain reference to those settings in the preface. **We were able to change “disaster and post-disaster areas” to “disaster-affected areas”,** which we were informed is more suitable.

10) Not focused on domestic research

The following comment was excellent, that Articles 4 (risk management plans) and 17 (insurance for local researchers) were written with a collaboration in mind, where at least one partner is in a high-income country, and can deliver on both requirements. This may not be the case if the fragile setting is located within a resource-limited country, where local researchers might not have the resources to adhere to Articles 4 and 17.

The articles now read as follows:

Article 4

Prior to the start of any field activities, researchers should be supported by their institution, **wherever possible**, to develop risk management plans to protect the physical integrity, mental wellbeing and safety of researchers, research participants and support teams. These plans should be tailored to the specific environment and, where feasible, include input from local collaborators on the research team.

Article 17

Where local members of the research team (e.g. gate keepers, interpreters, or field researchers) lack adequate protection mechanisms (like insurance), incoming researchers **from high income settings** should advocate to their host institution for extending the protections they receive to the whole team.

11) Not respecting local knowledge systems

The literature showed clearly that research in fragile settings can be patronising and not value local knowledge. This was emphasized again by one commentator. However, we believe that our Article 13 (formerly 12) covers this appropriately.

Article 13

Local knowledge and community acceptance are essential to conducting research that is respectful and not patronising. Researchers should ensure that research participants and local communities have opportunities to input local knowledge and perspectives meaningfully.

12) Alignment of values with articles

Good point that Article 21 could sit better under CARE. The article has been moved, even though it changes the entire numbering.

Article 21 **BETTER IN CARE**

It is the researchers' obligation to ensure that potential research participants understand that research activities are not part of humanitarian efforts. Where members of the research team have dual roles, they must clearly explain the distinction to potential research participants ('humanitarian misconception').

13) Translations, Alignments, Implementation Help

We completely agree that translations are needed and will do our best. Unfortunately, there is no more funding. The same applies to mapping the code against existing resources and the development of implementation aids such as case studies. For the latter, a forthcoming book about the development of the code will include the scoping reviews and the survey that form the basis of the TRUST Code Supplement.

14) Historical Trauma and Distrust

We agree that historical trauma and distrust can be major problems for equitable research in fragile settings. Of the four TRUST Family Ethics Codes, only the San Code of Research Ethics makes direct reference to this. (The San Code was drafted with support from the same leadership team as the TRUST Code Supplement). That's because the San Code can

refer to very specific instances of past research misconduct. We do not refer to historical trauma and distrust in this global code because it does not apply to all fragile settings.

15) Revisions

There are currently no mechanisms for the revision of the four TRUST Family Ethics Codes (TRUST Code, TRUST Code Supplement, PREPARED Code and San Code of Research Ethics). However, what is encouraging is that no revisions have been suggested, other than to the name of the title, for the TRUST Code, nor for the San Code of Research Ethics.

The final wording of the TRUST Code Supplement will also be influenced by comments from a professional editor who will focus on easy readability.

Thank you very much again for very valuable comments!

Doris Schroeder (on behalf of the development team)